

Characterization of Alumina—A Versatile Catalyst

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Different samples of alumina were prepared by impregnating pure alumina with potassium and fluoride ions and their heats of adsorption by adsorption of pyridine were determined by pulse flow technique in gas chromatograph in the temperature range 180-250°. The heats of adsorption decreased with addition of potassium and increased with addition of fluoride ions. Pure alumina had considerable total acidity; however, the Brønsted acidity was negligible.

Rate of dehydration of cyclohexanol was faster initially and decreased with increasing contact time. Cyclohexene, an intermediate, registered a maximum at an intermediate contact time and then began to fall, while 1- and 3-methylcyclopentenes kept on increasing; the concentration of 1-methylcyclopentene was always higher than that of 3-methylcyclopentene. The dehydration of cyclohexanol followed a first order kinetics.

The mechanism of transformation of cyclohexanol over alumina has been explained in terms of both Brønsted and Lewis acid sites.

A LUMINA as catalyst or as catalyst support finds multiple uses in several important industrial processes like, dehydration, isomerization, cracking, polymerization, condensation and alkylation¹. Alumina samples obtained from different sources are found to possess different activities². The presence of acid sites over alumina has been acknowledged, though the nature of acidity, whether Brønsted or Lewis type has been a point of controversy³⁻⁵. Further, reactivity and selectivity of the catalytic alumina change with the impregnation of alkali or halide ions^{1,6}.

An attempt has been made in the present work to correlate the activity of different alumina samples obtained by impregnation of pure alumina (from aluminium isopropoxide) with potassium and fluoride ions, with their heats of adsorption of pyridine, as it is a measure of the strength of acid sites. Cyclohexanol was chosen for this purpose because its transformation involves dehydration and skeletal and double bond isomerizations. Some of the steps are explained satisfactorily in terms of Lewis acid sites whose importance in bringing about various isomerization reactions has not been well recognised.

Experimental

Preparation of materials: Alumina A, was prepared by hydrolysing aluminium isopropoxide with distilled water⁷. The precipitated aluminium hydroxide was filtered, washed thoroughly, cut into cakes and dried at 120° for 24 hr. The dried material was then activated at 500° in a stream of pure air for another 24 hr. The activated catalyst was crushed, powdered and sieved to 40-60 mesh size. A part of this material was used as such under the label catalyst A, and the rest was modified with potassium or fluoride ions.

Aluminas B and C were obtained by doping alumina A with potassium nitrate solution in water to give 0.9 and 2.2% by weight of K⁺ as K₂O in the catalyst, respectively. Alumina D was prepared by impregnating alumina A with hydrofluoric acid (40% solution, E. Merck) to give 5% by weight of HF in the catalyst. The samples were dried and activated as described earlier.

Apparatus and procedure: The surface area (BET), pore volume and average pore radius of the catalysts were determined by low temperature adsorption of nitrogen⁸ and the results are presented in Table 1. The pulse flow technique of Eberly^{9,10} was used to measure the heats of adsorption of pyridine on the various aluminas in the temperature range 180-250° and the results are given in Table 2. The total

TABLE 1—SURFACE PROPERTIES OF THE CATALYSTS SUCH AS SURFACE AREA, PORE VOLUME AND AVERAGE PORE RADIUS

Catalyst	S _{BET} m ² /g	V _p ml/g	r A
A	139	0.435	55
B	129	—	—
C	135	0.275	40
D	125	0.442	60

TABLE 2—HEATS OF ADSORPTION OF PYRIDINE (ACIDITY INDEX) AND ACTIVATION ENERGY

Catalyst	Heat of adsorption kcal/mole (acidity index)	Activation energy kcal/mole
A	17.6	1.20
B	9.2	1.06
C	6.2	0.70
D	22.9	0.70

acidity of aluminas A and D was determined by *n*-butylamine titration methods of Johnson¹² and are found to be 0.650 and 1.240 m mole/g, respectively. Brønsted acidity of alumina A was found to be only 0.02 m mole/g by potassium iodide-potassium iodate method¹³.

The reactions were carried out in a flow type fixed bed reactor. The operating variables, such as space velocity and particle size, were so chosen as to eliminate diffusion control on the reaction rate. The products were identified by Perkin-Elmer Infracord Model-137 and Perkin-Elmer Vapour Fractometer-154D and estimated using a 2 metre column of Bentone-34 in the Vapour Fractometer-154D.

Results and Discussion

The heat of adsorption of pure alumina is found to decrease markedly from 17.6 kcal to 9.2 kcal by the addition of 0.9% by weight of potassium ions. When the doping increases to 2.2% the heat of adsorption falls still further to 6.2 kcal. On the other hand impregnation of alumina A with fluoride ions increases the heat of adsorption from 17.6 kcal to 22.9 kcal.

If the acidic sites on alumina are visualized as protons of the Al-O-H bond (Brønsted acid site), potassium, by replacing the protons in the hydroxyl group, reduces the concentration of Brønsted sites as shown below

Lewis acidity of the dehydrated alumina surface has been explained on the basis of incompletely coordinated aluminium atoms, and its formation is suggested to be as follows :

Introduction of potassium ions in the places of hydrogen during the preparation of the catalyst suppresses the formation of Lewis sites. This explains the lower heats of adsorption in the cases of aluminas B and C.

Hydrofluoric acid can enhance the acidic strength of the active sites in one or both of the following ways¹³ :

In scheme A, the acidity of the proton is enhanced by the polarization induced in the adjacent bond by fluorine. In addition, the positive charge on the proton will be stabilized by the partial negative charge on fluorine. In scheme B, the fluorine attached to Al₍₂₎ polarises the Al-O-Al bonds in the manner illustrated above and increases the Lewis acid strength of Al₍₁₎.

The influence of contact time (W/F) on the rate of dehydration of cyclohexanol and the formation of products has been studied at 375° over alumina A and the results are illustrated in Fig. 1. The rate of dehydration is faster in the lower contact time regions. It decreases slowly and remains constant beyond 0.3 hr. The concentration of cyclohexene increases in the product, registers a maximum around 0.05 hr, and falls with further increase in contact time. Methylcyclopentenes begin to appear after 0.1 hr and keep on increasing; the concentration of 1-methylcyclopentene is always higher than that of 3-methylcyclopentene.

Fig. 1. Influence of contact time on the reactions of cyclohexanol; Catalyst Alumina A, Temp. 375°.

The effects of acidity index and temperature on the overall conversion of cyclohexanol are shown in Fig. 2. Increase in the acidity index of the catalyst and reaction temperature increases the conversion of cyclohexanol. However, at a fixed acidity index, more cyclohexanol reacted at higher temperature. Even though dehydration occurred over low acidity index alumina, it increased considerably with increasing acidity.

The extents of different reactions such as dehydration, skeletal isomerization and double bond isomerization as a function of acidity index are illustrated in Table 3. The most striking features of these results are the different rates at which the activity of aluminas in the various reactions are suppressed when its acidity is progressively reduced. The dehydration activity decreased steadily with increasing additions of potassium ions, while the skeletal and double bond isomerization activities fell

Fig. 2. Influence of acidity index and temp. on the conversion of cyclohexanol.

TABLE 3—COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT REACTIONS SUCH AS DEHYDRATION, SKELETAL ISOMERIZATION AND DOUBLE BOND ISOMERIZATION AS FUNCTION OF ACIDITY INDEX; TEMP. 375°, CONTACT TIME 0.52 hr.

Acidity Index kcal/mole	6.2	9.2	17.6	22.9
Dehydration (mole %)	43.00	51.00	68.00	75.00
Skeletal isomerization (mole %)	0.00	4.00	55.00	55.00
Double bond isomerization (mole %)	0.00	0.00	20.00	20.00

sharply; the fall in the double bond isomerization activity is greater than that of skeletal isomerization activity.

The selectivity ratio (SR) of the catalyst as a function of acidity is given in Fig. 3. The concentration of cyclohexene drastically decreased with increasing acidity index of the catalyst while the concentration of methylcyclopentenes increased and consequently the selectivity ratio decreased.

Fig. 3. Influence of acidity index on the selectivity ratio.

The kinetics of dehydration of cyclohexanol over alumina A has been followed by plotting $-\ln(1-X_A)$ (where X_A is the mole fraction of cyclohexanol disappeared) against contact time W/F at 375° (where W is the weight of the catalyst and F is the amount of cyclohexanol fed into the reactor per hour). The plot gives a straight line (Fig. 4) indicating that the reaction follows a first order kinetics. The rate constant calculated from the slope of the first order plot is 2.065 hr^{-1} . The variation of rate constant with temperature is illustrated in Fig. 5 and the energy of activation computed from the slopes of the Arrhenius plots are recorded in Table 2.

Fig. 4. First order plot; catalyst Alumina A, Temp. 375°.

Fig. 5. Arrhenius plots.

Mechanism: Both Dewing³ and Pearson⁴ claim to have detected the presence of Brönsted acid centres on alumina while Knözinger⁵ has concluded that alumina possesses no such species. The presence of Lewis acid sites over alumina surfaces and also its importance in bringing about reactions, such as

different types of isomerizations of olefins¹⁴ are well recognized. Further, determination of acidity of alumina shows that it possesses a very significant amount of total acidity. However, the presence of Brønsted acidity is much too small (vide Experimental). In view of the above, the mechanisms of reactions involving the transformation of cyclohexanol are explained both by Brønsted and Lewis acid sites.

The reaction of cyclohexanol is known to proceed by a consecutive reaction, in which cyclohexene, formed initially by dehydration of cyclohexanol, undergoes skeletal isomerization to 1-methylcyclopentene. This may subsequently isomerize to 3-methylcyclopentene by shifting of double bond.

The mechanism involves initial protonation of cyclohexanol, the proton coming from the Brønsted acid site of the catalyst, followed by dehydration

with the formation of a carbonium ion. Cyclohexene desorbs from the surface with simultaneous elimination of a proton. The cyclohexene adsorbs onto a Lewis acid site resulting in the formation of a carbonium ion which suffers skeletal isomerization involving a less stable primary carbonium ion, which rearranges to a more stable tertiary carbonium ion by 1,2-hydride shift. This then desorbs as 1-methylcyclopentene. The 1-methylcyclopentene is attacked by a proton leading to the formation of a tertiary carbonium ion, which changes to a secondary carbonium ion by 1,3-hydride shift. This eliminates a proton giving rise to 3-methylcyclopentene. The fact that 1,3-hydride shift is not so easy as the 1,2-hydride shift, accounts for the lower concentration of 3-methylcyclopentene.

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